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Marine energy, communities, and economies: Asking stakeholders the right questions to address data gaps

Jillian Eller^a, Linda D'Anna^{b,1}, Lindsay Dubbs^c

^aEast Carolina University, Integrated Coastal Sciences Ph.D. Program, 1000 E. 5th St., Greenville, NC 27858, USA

^bEast Carolina University, Integrated Coastal Programs, Coastal Studies Institute, 850 NC 345, Wanchese, NC 27981, USA

^cUniversity of North Carolina at Chapel Hill and the Coastal Studies Institute, 850 NC 345, Wanchese, NC 27981, USA

Abstract

Marine energy resources exist in close proximity to working waterfronts and coastal communities where this energy could be used by a range of small off-grid applications. However, stakeholder engagement conducted by the Atlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC), the newest National Marine Energy Center, reveals a disconnect between the data needs of marine energy researchers and information sharing by potential marine energy end-users. Marine energy developers and researchers indicated that they have questions and require data about energy needs from end users, including coastal communities, but do not have the means to connect with end-users and make data requests. To fill the gap between researchers and end-users, the AMEC Stakeholder Engagement team and research group utilizes a collaborative industry-academia model for translating marine energy research data needs to non-experts. We share and promote best practices for communicating technical information to nontechnical audiences, including practices related to transparency of intentions, relationship building, and utilizing context-appropriate word choices. Information collected from research participants, including conference attendees, is analyzed to assess how marine energy researchers explain their research and data needs to non-experts and whether the explanations are appropriate for their target audiences. Conference attendees will have the option to participate in ongoing research and benefit from an iterative learning process to refine their messages that will prepare them to be better communicators with marine communities and economies. Our research builds and strengthens the networks among marine energy industry, academia, and end users, and supports the marine energy industry to connect with maritime applications and non-experts to advance the field of marine energy.

Keywords: marine energy; communication best practices; knowledge co-production

^{1*} Linda D'Anna
dannal15@ecu.edu

1. Introduction

Marine energy resources exist in close proximity to working waterfronts and coastal communities where this energy could be used by a range of small off-grid applications, including maritime industries and blue economies. However, stakeholder engagement conducted by the Atlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC), the newest National Marine Energy Center, reveals a disconnect between marine energy researchers, industry experts working to harness energy resources, and potential marine energy end-users. Marine energy developers and researchers who have accepted the AMEC Universe Invitation to Engage (<https://www.amec-us.org/the-amec-universe>) indicated that they have questions and require data about energy needs from end-users, including coastal communities, but do not have the means to connect with end-users and make data requests. These questions and data interests ranged from electricity usage and energy infrastructure to current and desired energy storage specifics.

Scientific experts must be able to clearly share knowledge and engage in two-way communication to successfully acquire information from non-experts. The tendency for scientists to rely solely on education to seek input from individuals outside of their discipline is shown to be unsuccessful [1,2]. Scholars advocate that a paradigm shift towards mutual learning in the ways experts interact with non-experts aligns scientific advancements with decision-making and action [2]. Recent discussions from the medical field recommend proactive approaches that scientists and engineers can develop to promote dialog-based models of communication for public engagement, including building relationships, sharing information beyond their expert scope, and committing to listening and learning from diverse audiences [3]. Simply put, two-way communication between experts and non-experts is based on the cultivation of trust built by scientists.

Building trust and effective communication are closely intertwined; trust cannot be created without communication between involved parties, and authentic reception and response to dialog is dependent on trust. Relationships are the foundation of trust that link science communication and experts' need for public participation to coproduce knowledge [1,3]. Forming relationships with non-experts necessitates a scientist's ability to be transparent in their intentions, engage in active listening, and gain credibility in their field [4]. While fostering relationships to build trust requires time and the input of all those involved, a scientist can consider how they would want to be communicated with if the roles were reversed, as described by the golden rule: treat others the way you would want to be treated.

In addition to building trust and communicating effectively, experts must understand their audience and modify their approach to gain the information they seek [1]. The context of communication and the identities of the individuals communicating influences the way communication is received more than the actual content of the conversation [5]. Practicing empathy for the other in the way one speaks with non-experts can be more significant than the individual components of speech or conversation, akin to the sum being greater than the parts. Scientific innovations are achievable when experts consider and validate the experiences of the targeted audience as crucial to the scientific process [3].

Innovation and problem-solving are hallmark outcomes of two-way communication between scientists and the public. The medical field exemplifies the benefits of public involvement in research including improving the research process, enhancing participation in behavioral programs, and expanding participant diversity [6]. The results of public collaboration in governance extend to proposing creative solutions and establishing trust with local government, as well as echoing the sentiments from the medical field of boosting participation overall [7]. A literature review on public engagement in wind energy reveals that two-way communication in the industry can advance research and design and allows for the creation of cooperatively financed projects [8]. These cases highlight the research potential of effective communication between experts and non-experts.

Studies investigating how experts interact with individuals and groups outside of their domain span disparate fields; however, there remains a distinct gap in the literature addressing how researchers and engineers obtain data from non-experts to develop new technologies. Furthermore, there is a deficit of investigations into how the marine energy developers exchange knowledge with end-users in maritime applications. To address these gaps, our research team is exploring how marine energy researchers and developers ask questions to elicit data from blue economies and coastal communities.

2. Methodology

Our research group utilizes a collaborative industry-academia model for translating the data needs and informational queries of experts conducting marine energy research for non-technical audiences. Participants in our research, including attendees of the session, are asked to consider the following question: "What data do you need from blue economies, coastal communities, or other relevant lay audiences?", and then write digital or electronic

“minute papers” expressing these needs at an 8th-grade level. A minute paper, as the name implies, is a short written piece that the writer spends a few minutes conceiving of and then a few minutes writing out.

Based on a review of relevant academic and gray literature, we will share best practices for communicating technical information to non-technical audiences. Research conducted in the last decade on the subject of science communication informs the protocol suggested by this study. Sources pertaining to scientists and engineers communicating to the public through asking questions and two-way communication were included for their relevance to the topic. Additionally, investigations into preparing scientific communications were utilized to create a framework for best practices.

3. Results and Discussion

The proposed methodology will aid our research team in answering the overarching question: “How do marine energy researchers explain their research and data needs to non-experts?”. Based on a review of minute papers by a group of non-experts, this study will determine if the requests presented in the minute papers are appropriate for the target audiences. Analysis of the minute papers will allow us to examine who marine energy researchers are seeking to engage with, the specific type of data requested, and how requests for data from non-experts are made. Conference attendees will have the option to participate in ongoing research. Those who opt-in will benefit from an iterative learning process with us that will prepare them to be better communicators with marine communities and economies.

Human experience and artificial intelligence will help to determine if the requests presented in the minute papers use language accessible to target their audience, including being free of jargon. Based on the review of communication between scientists and non-experts, best practices for communicating across and between groups was consolidated into a framework, adapted from [4] (Table 1). Productive requests for information from non-experts must include specificity about one’s goals, an awareness of the recipient’s knowledge base, and intentional word choice. Steps outlined in best practices provide details about a scientist’s need to prepare, be cognizant about their approach, clarify their request, and implement their communication plan.

Table 1. Best practices framework for communication between scientists and non-experts, adapted from [4].

Steps	Details	Description
Preparation	Specify request	What kind of interaction are you seeking?
	Understand the recipient	What is the level of understanding your audience has about the topic? What beliefs do they already have about the work? [5]
	Choose the appropriate format and time of the request	The format and timing of the interaction depends upon the request you are making. While some interactions may be appropriate for digital engagement through email, other requests will necessitate a real-time conversation, depending on the complexity, relationship to the recipient, and availability of the recipient.
	Practice making the request	Rehearse the request, either alone or optimally to others that are not familiar with the topic. Anticipate aspects of the request that may need further explanation.
Approach	Seek to build trust	Utilize transparency as a means to build trust in communication.
	Listen to understand	Encourage the participation of audience members and actively listen for their unique contribution.
	Be aware of the positionality of power	Engage with others as an equal [1].

	Solicit feedback and incorporate it into future requests	Depending on the circumstances, ask the recipient for input on your approach, including their perception and suggestions for others to engage.
Clarifying the request	Avoid jargon	Choose plain language instead of technical jargon.
	Be concise	While still maintaining transparency, deliberately maintain focus in communicating with others.
	Use appropriate analogies, real-life examples, and metaphors in communicating	Connecting aspects of the request with relevant and relatable examples.
	Incorporate visual aids	When available, use visual resources and aids in communicating.
Implementation	Be considerate of their time	Recognize the value of other's time.
	Contextualize the request	Provide a broad overview of the research, avoiding details irrelevant to the current request.
	Reflect mutual learning by paraphrasing the discussion	Respond appropriately to the other's concerns and validate the shared knowledge [1].
	Define the next steps and follow through with the commitment	Be accountable to any requests for follow-up the recipient has made. Describe what will happen as a result of the knowledge generated during the conversation.

Results from the review reinforce trust and relationships as pivotal in generating the conditions to make requests of non-experts; however, word choice is considered when relaying information directly between individuals. Experts asking questions must be diligent in avoiding their use of jargon, as some specific terminology may be appropriate, aiding in the process of learning for the recipient, while others may be superfluous and detract from the overall interaction between experts and non-experts [9]. The judicious use of jargon may be refined through linguistic techniques to convey meaning, such as using analogies, illustrating through examples, explaining terms, and utilizing colloquial phrases accessible to a larger audience [10].

4. Conclusion

Bridging the divide between marine energy researchers and their data requests of coastal communities, including end users of the Blue Economy, is part of the work of the AMEC Stakeholder Engagement team. The goal of this research is to build and strengthen the networks among the marine energy industry, academia, and end-users. Our research will support the marine energy industry and researchers to connect with maritime applications and non-experts to advance the field of marine energy as they Power the Blue Economy. The outcomes of ongoing research will evaluate the impact of best practices on the requests scientists have for non-experts.

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References

- [1] Cook BR, Overpeck JT. Relationship-building between climate scientists and publics as an alternative to information transfer. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change* 2019; **10**(2):e570.
- [2] Houtman D, Vijlbrief B, Riedijk S. Experts in science communication. *EMBO Reports* 2021; **22**(8):e52988.
- [3] Reincke CM, Bredenoord AL, van Mil MH. From deficit to dialogue in science communication. *EMBO Reports* 2020; **21**(9):e51278.
- [4] Nussbaum FG. Successful Communication of Complex Information. *White paper: Communication of Complex Information*; 2023. p 1-13.
- [5] van der Sanden MC, Meijman FJ. SISSA-International School for Advanced Studies Article A step-by-step approach for science communication practitioners: a design perspective. *Journal of Science Communication*, 2012; **11**:1–9.
- [6] Holmes L, Cresswell K, Williams S, Parsons S, Keane A, Wilson C, Islam S, Joseph O, Miah J, Robinson E, Starling B. Innovating public engagement and patient involvement through strategic collaboration and practice. *Research Involvement and Engagement* 2019; **5**:30.
- [7] Bartoletti R, Faccioli F. Public Engagement, Local Policies, and Citizens' Participation: An Italian Case Study of Civic Collaboration. *Social Media and Society* 2016;**2**: 1-11.
- [8] Solman H, Smits M, van Vliet B, Bush S. Co-production in the wind energy sector: A systematic literature review of public engagement beyond invited stakeholder participation. *Energy Research and Social Science* 2021; **72**: 101876.
- [9] Russell H. Scientific Jargon, Good and Bad. *J. Technical Writing and Communication*, 2003; **33**:201–229.
- [10] Hinko K, Seneca J, Finkelstein N. *Use of Scientific Language by University Physics Students Communicating to the Public*. 2021. p. 1-4.